

FUNCTIONS OF LANGUAGE: TRANSACTIONAL AND INTERACTIONAL PERSPECTIVE

Narzulloeva Gulyuz Qahramon qizi, Supervisor Sadikova Dildora Nizomovna

The student of Navoiy state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20446056>

Annotation. *Language serves multiple functions in human communication, of which the distinction between transactional and interactional functions is particularly important in discourse analysis and language teaching. While the transactional function focuses on the effective communication of factual or propositional information to achieve specific goals, the interactional function focuses on maintaining and establishing social relationships, expressing personal relationships, and building rapport. This article analyzes these two approaches, mainly based on the Brown and Yule model, and considers their relevance for oral speech, language pedagogy, and real-life communication. By analyzing the characteristics and examples of each function, the study shows that most natural communication combines both functions, but one of them often dominates depending on the context. Understanding this duality increases communicative competence and helps to formulate effective teaching methods.*

Keywords: *transactional and interactional function of language, social relations, information transfer.*

Аннотация. *Язык выполняет множество функций в человеческой коммуникации, и различие между транзакционной и интеракционной функциями особенно важно в дискурсивном анализе и преподавании языка. В то время как транзакционная функция фокусируется на эффективной передаче фактической или пропозициональной информации для достижения конкретных целей, интеракционная функция фокусируется на поддержании и установлении социальных отношений, выражении личных отношений и построении взаимопонимания. В данной статье анализируются эти два подхода, в основном на основе модели Брауна и Юла, и рассматривается их актуальность для устной речи, языковой педагогики и реальной коммуникации. Анализируя характеристики и примеры каждой функции, исследование показывает, что большинство видов естественной коммуникации сочетают обе функции, но одна из них часто доминирует в зависимости от контекста. Понимание этой двойственности повышает коммуникативную компетентность и помогает в разработке эффективных методов обучения.*

Ключевые слова: *транзакционная и интерактивная функция языка, социальные отношения, передача информации.*

Annotatsiya. *Til inson muloqotida bir nechta funktsiyalarni bajaradi, ulardan tranzaksiya va interaktiv funktsiyalar o'rtasidagi farq, ayniqsa, nutq tahlili va til o'qitishda muhimdir. Tranzaksiya funktsiyasi aniq maqsadlarga erishish uchun faktik yoki taklif ma'lumotlarini samarali etkazishga qaratilgan bo'lsa, interaktiv funktsiya ijtimoiy munosabatlarni saqlash va o'rnatish, shaxsiy munosabatlarni ifoda etish va o'zaro munosabatlarni o'rnatishga qaratilgan. Ushbu maqolada asosan Braun va Yule modeliga asoslangan ushbu ikki yondashuv tahlil qilinadi va ularning og'zaki nutq, til pedagogikasi va real hayotdagi muloqot uchun ahamiyati ko'rib chiqiladi. Har bir funktsiyaning xususiyatlari va misollarini tahlil qilish orqali tadqiqot shuni*

ko'rsatadiki, ko'pgina tabiiy muloqot ikkala funktsiyani birlashtiradi, ammo ulardan biri ko'pincha kontekstga qarab ustunlik qiladi. Ushbu ikkilikni tushunish kommunikativ kompetentsiyani oshiradi va samarali o'qitish usullarini shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: *tilning tranzaksiyaviy va interaktiv funktsiyasi, ijtimoiy munosabatlar, axborot uzatish.*

Introduction

Language is not simply a system of signs, but a multifunctional tool that people use for various purposes in their social and cognitive lives. Among the various classifications of language functions proposed by linguists, the distinction between transactional and interactional approaches is a practical and influential one, especially in the analysis of spoken discourse.

Brown and Yule (1983) provide a clear analytical framework for describing the main functions of language: "We call the function in which language serves to express 'content' transactional, and the function in which it is concerned with the expression of social relations and personal relationships interactional." They also argue that this division is useful for analysis: "We adopt only two terms to describe the main functions of language, and we emphasize that this division is an analytical convenience."

From the transactional perspective, language is used primarily to convey factual or propositional information. Brown and Yule (1983) define it as follows: "We call language primarily transactional language that is used to convey 'factual or propositional information.' In primarily transactional language, we assume that the speaker (or writer)'s primary purpose is to convey information effectively." Success in such discourse is measured by how clearly the message is understood and can be put into practice with minimal misunderstanding.

In contrast, the interactional perspective focuses on the social and relational aspects of communication. According to Brown and Yule (1983), interactional language serves "the phatic use of language: its use to establish and maintain social relationships." They illustrate this point with a clear example: "If two strangers are quivering in the cold wind at a bus stop and one of them looks at the other and says, 'ohh, that's so cold,' it is unlikely that the speaker's primary purpose is to convey information. More likely, the speaker is expressing a willingness to be friendly and to engage in conversation." Thus, interactional speech acts as the "lubricant of social mechanisms," helping to establish roles, express solidarity, and maintain harmonious relationships.

This distinction, proposed by Brown and Yule, is also broadly consistent with previous functional binaries in linguistics. As they note: "Our 'transactional/interactional' distinction is broadly consistent with functional binaries such as Bühler's (1934) representational/expressive', Jakobson's (1960) 'referential/emotional', Halliday's (1970b) 'ideational/interpersonal', and Lyons' (1977) 'descriptive/social-expressive'."

Although this distinction is presented as a binary for analytical purposes, Brown and Yule argue that purely transactional or purely interactional speech is rarely encountered in natural communication. Most spoken communication contains elements of both functions, with one usually dominating depending on the context and communicative purpose.

The transactional and interactional approaches are important for discourse analysis, sociolinguistics, and especially language teaching. Traditional language teaching has often focused too much on transactional skills (such as giving instructions or asking for information) and

underdeveloped the interactional skills needed for real social interaction. A balanced approach that develops both functions is essential for building real communicative competence.

This article reviews the theoretical foundations of these two functions, provides examples from every day and institutional discourse, and discusses their pedagogical application in English language teaching.

1. Basic Theories of Functions of Transaction and Interaction.

Brown and Yule (1983) explicitly draw this distinction and point to its fruitfulness as an analytic strategy. In their own words, “We will call the function that language serves when it is used to express ‘content’ transactional, and we will call the function that language serves when it is used to express social relationships and personal feelings interactional”. Brown and Yule also explain that transactional language is the type of language that is mainly used to share 'factual or propositional information' [Brown and Yule, 1983, page. 20]. Most of the time when people are just talking or writing to get information across, their main concern is to make sure that the message is getting across clearly. The key aim in these situations is to convey information rapidly.

People often judge how well a message works by whether the information received was correct. Getting things wrong can create problems in real life, such as giving the wrong directions, medical advice, or scientific details. Brown and Yule (1983) refer to the interactive function as the phatic use of language and they give an example. When two strangers are standing at a bus stop in the cold wind and one says *Ohh, that's so cold*, this is not primarily to exchange information but rather to establish a friendly link and to start a conversation. They think of interactional language as a lubricant of social processes – it helps to establish roles, show support, and keep relationships.

The authors do not consider this division to be rigid but a convenient way of arranging ideas. They emphasize that: “We shall use only two terms for the principal functions of language and we shall indicate that this separation is only a convenient device for analysis. A sentence in natural language is unlikely to be used for one purpose only, ignoring the other. Similarly, people feel that in real conversations these two functions are not generally separate or different. “Speech that is purely about getting things done, or purely about establishing a relationship is rare,” they say. This idea also corresponds to other traditional models in the study of language. For example, in M.A.K. Halliday’s functional model shows that language can do many things at the same time. Halliday points out that language has developed to meet human needs and that its structure is designed to fulfill those needs.

Transactional language is more about sharing information and experiences, which is part of the ideational function. Interactional language, on the other hand, deals with managing relationships and how people connect with each other, which is part of the interpersonal function. According to Halliday, the interpersonal function is about building, keeping, and defining relationships between people in a society.

Roman Jakobson (1960) identified two main functions of language: the referential function, which deals with context and sharing information, and the phatic function, which is about keeping communication going.

Jakobson describes the phatic function as follows: "There are messages primarily serving to establish, prolong, or discontinue communication, to check whether the channel works..." This definition further reinforces the distinction between transactional (**referential**) and interactional (**phatic**).

2. Characteristics and Examples.

Transactional language is focused on achieving a specific goal, needs to be clear, logical, and efficient. In it, getting the information right is very important. Examples:

- a) In a store: "I want three kilos of bananas and half a kilo of peach, please."
- b) In the workplace: "The meeting is set for 12 a.m. tomorrow in Room 201". Please bring the quarterly report.
- c) When giving directions, say: "Go straight, turn right at the traffic lights, and the bus station will be on your left." In such kind of situations, success comes from clearly sharing information so that there is little chance of confusion.

Interactional speech is used to keep and strengthen social connections. It usually includes friendly words and shows how people feel about each other. Examples:

- a) Among friends: "Hey, how's it going? Long time no see! "You look great!"
- b) When talking to a stranger at the station: "Nice weather today, isn't it?" or "Oh, that's so cold."
- c) In a family chat: "How was your day, dear?"(mostly to keep the connection warm).

Brown and Yule (1983) say that in real conversations, these two functions usually happen at the same time, but one of them is more important. For example, in a friendly chat, even though people mostly talk and interact with each other, they can also share important information like what they need to do or arrange. In contrast, during a formal meeting, even though the main focus is on getting things done, people still use friendly expressions like greetings and goodbyes at the start or end of the conversation.

3. Relevance to Spoken Discourse and Language Teaching

These two functions are especially important in spoken conversation because when people talk, it happens right away and is heavily influenced by the situation around them.

Transactional speech is often used in places like schools, work meetings, and doctor visits, while interactional speech is more typical in regular and daily conversations with friends and family. Traditional methods of teaching language, which are called language pedagogy, usually pay more attention to skills that involve exchanging information, like doing activities where people have different information or acting out situations to give directions. However, they don't give enough attention to skills that involve interacting in a more personal way, such as having casual conversations, building good relationships, or sharing personal opinions. So, even if students speak correctly in grammar, they might have some problems communicating in real life situations. Historiographic Metafiction and Blurred Realities-The novel exemplifies historiographic metafiction, a hallmark of postmodernism, by interweaving factual historical references with fictional speculation. Brown treats historical events, religious texts, and art as malleable constructs, reinterpreting them to challenge orthodox narratives. For instance, he questions the divinity of Jesus Christ, suggesting his marriage to Mary Magdalene and the suppression of this "truth" by early Christian institutions. This revisionist approach destabilizes the authority of the Bible, framing it as a historically biased document rather than an infallible truth. The inclusion of real-world sources like Holy Blood, Holy Grail and the Dead Sea Scrolls further blurs the line between fact and fiction, inviting readers to question historical certainty

Modern language teaching methods, like Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) focus on enhancing both the ability to use language in any situations and the skills needed to communicate effectively with people. As an example, transactional exercises include tasks where information is shared and activities that involve solving problems. Interactional exercises include

free conversation, sharing opinions, and practicing social English expressions such as greetings and back-channeling phrases like "Really?" or "That's interesting." Teachers can help students become better at communicating by teaching them to tell the difference between the two functions. This is especially helpful and also useful for people learning English as a second language, while they usually need to speak in a suitable as well as accurate way.

In linguistics, the difference between transactional and interactional functions of language is still a key way to analyze language. Brown and Yule (1983) mention that this distinction isn't completely clear-cut, but it still plays an important role in analyzing conversations, studying how people speak, and teaching language. In most normal conversations, the two functions work together, but depending on the situation, one might be more important than the other. Knowing this difference is important for more than just language experts and teachers. It matters to everyone because good communication isn't just about sharing information. It's also about maintaining and building relationships with others. Future studies might look more into how these two functions vary across nations and how people communicate online with each other.

References

1. Brown, G., & Yule, G. (1983). *Discourse Analysis*. Cambridge University Press.
2. Halliday, M. A. K. (1970). *Language Structure and Language Function*. J. Lyons (ed.), *New Horizons in Linguistics* (pp. 140–165). Penguin.
(Discusses ideational and interpersonal metafunctions, consistent with transactional and interactional usage.)
3. Jakobson, R. (1960). *Final Statement: Linguistics and Poetics*. T. A. Sebeok (ed.), *Style in Language* (pp. 350–377). MIT Press.
(Introduces referential and phatic functions of language.)
4. McCarthy, M. (1991). *Discourse Analysis for Language Teachers*. Cambridge University Press.
(Provides practical explanations of transactional and interactive language and their importance in teaching.)
5. Nunan, D. (1991). *Language Teaching Methodology: A Textbook for Teachers*. Prentice Hall.
(Discusses the importance of balancing transactional and interactive skills in communicative language teaching.)
6. Sadikova Dildora Nizomovna. 2025 "THE INTERTEXTUAL NATURE OF SYMBOLS IN DAN BROWN'S NOVELS". *RUSSIA- SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND EDUCATION* 1(4):15-20. <https://e-conferences.org/index.php/rus/article/view/271>.